

Venture Capital as a New Way of Funding Technology Startups in Uzbekistan

Khurshidabonu Saydullaeva ✉

Software Engineer at EPAM Systems, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT:

This article analyzes the importance of venture capital as an alternative source of investment for entrepreneurs to build their startups and the current state of the startup ecosystem in Uzbekistan. It explores how venture finance is changing in Uzbekistan, looking at new models and recent advancements reshaping the country's startup scene. Through a detailed analysis of public policy, trends in private investment, and the growth of startup ecosystems, this study highlights the revolutionary impact of venture capital on Uzbekistan's economy. By offering case studies of successful ventures and assessing the opportunities and constraints inherent in this dynamic landscape, it also provides insights into the future of venture capital in Uzbekistan and its role in supporting innovation and entrepreneurship.

Keywords: technology startups, venture capital, investment, incubators, accelerators, business angels.

Suggested Citation: K. Saydullaeva, "Venture Capital as a New Way of Funding Technology Startups in Uzbekistan," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(6), pp. 200-204, Nov-Dec 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(6\).20](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(6).20)

INTRODUCTION

Digital technologies play a vital role in our lives today as we use digital services everywhere, for example, to order food, taxi, book appointments with doctor, shop at marketplaces, promote our services and products on social media, etc. Unlike other businesses, tech businesses require developing digital products in the form of applications or websites, sometimes with the latest technologies like AI, blockchain, or machine learning. The period of development can last for several months, which is hard to maintain financially and the risk of not getting profits is high, or profiting from the business may require several years. Therefore to start building a tech startup, business owners either need to use their self-investments or ask help from their family members and friends, because many banks are mostly reluctant to give loans to startups because of the high risk of loss. They can consider crowdfunding like most startups do where crowdfunding is developed, but this investment tool is underdeveloped and unpopular in Uzbekistan.

One of the key instruments for financing innovative entrepreneurial activity, especially in the early stages, is venture funds. Their work is based on the accumulation of funds from various sources and their further distribution for the development of innovative projects and enterprises. Venture capital is accumulated in special venture funds (venture capital funds) through collective investments of individual investors – venture capitalists or business angels – private investors who, unlike conventional venture capitalists, start-ups are financed at a very early stage of development, often at the idea stage. Other participants in venture funds are corporations and institutional investors (institutions) – pension funds, insurance companies, etc. All elements of the venture financing system - startups, investors, strategic buyers, legislative framework, and infrastructure supporting business development - combined into a single venture ecosystem [1].

Giant and most valuable companies like Apple, Microsoft, Alphabet, Amazon, Tesla, Meta, and Nvidia are all technology companies and they financed their early stage of development with venture capital [2]. Considering that Uzbekistan can benefit a lot from encouraging VC funds and providing a good ecosystem for emerging startups.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Most of the articles and publications on startups and venture capital in Uzbekistan started in 2020. Likely, this reflects improved data availability on VC and increased use of methods that control for selection into VC in recent years. Most studies focused on the importance of venture capital in the economic growth of the country mentioned problems and gave some solutions to them. Only the report filed for the Asian Development Bank by Dilshod Zufarov with the assistance of Aimee Hampel-Milagrosa, Vishal Aditya Potluri, and Paul Vandenberg about Uzbekistan's ecosystem for tech startups, covered many insights on outcomes of the reforms and the overview of the venture capital market, surveying 31 startups. Another open report from UzVC provided key analytical findings from 2022 and 2023, covering investments that came from Uzbekistan VCs to startups outside Uzbekistan, as well as grants local startups received from government and international agencies, have been taken into consideration when evaluating the national VC market volume. Other useful resources consist of the official websites of VCs, ministries, and IT Park.

METHODOLOGY

The methodologies for examining current scientific literature regarding the application of venture capital to finance startups in Uzbekistan, study of statistical data, economic comparison and data grouping, are widely used. A comprehensive review of pertinent laws and regulations has also been conducted, ensuring that the analysis is grounded in the legal context that governs venture capital activities in Uzbekistan. This multifaceted approach not only enriches the understanding of the current state of venture capital in the region but also identifies opportunities and challenges for startups seeking financing.

DISCUSSION & FINDINGS

Tech startups are innovative enterprises that have developed new technology or are using existing technology to create a unique business model. Most startups are highly scalable, allowing them to grow rapidly, especially if they are internet-based and can replicate their services to attract thousands or millions of customers. Rapid growth potential is a defining characteristic of a startup. It's critical to understand that startups go through multiple phases of development. Every level has different difficulties and calls for different kinds of assistance. These stages (and their number) go by different names according to different specialists, but the consensus is as follows [4]:

1. Seed stage: This is the stage where the business develops an idea, defining the purposes and features of the product and the business model. In this phase, most startups are self-funded but can also attract angel investments and government grants.
2. Development stage: This is about building a team and developing a minimum viable product (MVP) and market validation. The investment can come from venture capital and business angels.
3. Scaling stage: During this phase, entrepreneurs aim to get more traction within the intended market. At this point, funding from private equity and venture capital funds is necessary. The startup may also apply for a bank loan given that it is profitable and has assets to use as collateral.

It is hard to track the number of startups by each stage now because there is no central database for the startup information and many seed-stage startups are not registered as legal entities. However according to the report by UZVCA(Uzbekistan Venture Capital Association)[5], in 2020, roughly 90% of all startups were in the seed stage, while 8% and 2% of them were in development and scaling stages respectively(see Table 1). As mentioned in the report, companies like Avtoelon.uz, LeBazar, Jowi, OSON, BILLZ, CLICK, MyTaxi were in the pool of scaling startups. Also,

most of the startup founders were concentrating on the capital - Tashkent city, taking up almost 56%, compared to other cities in Uzbekistan. We can also see that the gender gap was significant, with men consisting of 97% of all founders. The leading sectors of the startups were FinTech and Marketplace.

Table 1. Number of Startups by Stage, 2020

Stage	Number of Startups, app.	Share of Total (%)	Annual Increase
Seed	1200	90	200
Development	100	8	30
Scaling	20	2	2
Total	1320	100	232

Since 2016, Uzbekistan started to open to the global market, decreasing the heavy reliance on raw materials, instead encouraging technology, economic diversification, and private sector development. As venture funds were a new practice for both investors and young entrepreneurs, there was no reliable legislation. The reforms started with the Action Strategy 2017–2021, including sectors like banking, taxation, trade, and privatization of state-owned enterprises. The government created the "Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in 2015, which was reestablished as "Ministry of Digital Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in 2022. Especially the establishment of the IT Park in 2019, contributed significantly to the increase of IT services export and fostered the improvement of the startup ecosystem in Uzbekistan. The Law on Innovation Activity was enacted in 2020, which shed light on the rights of venture organizations. In July 2022, the Innovative Development Strategy 2022-2026, was approved, which aimed to fund 75 billion SUM to 122 startup projects [4]. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 303 of 29.05.2024 [6], from July 1, 2024, based on an annual competition to support start-up projects in the field of IT education services, production of software products and export orientation, through the Technological Park of Software Products and Information Technologies, the government will allocate grants up to 1 billion soums, in a following manner:

- ▶ for a promising idea - 150 million soums;
- ▶ for a project specializing in the local market - 300 million soums;
- ▶ for a project specializing in the world market - 1 billion soums;

A long-awaited legislation “On measures for further development of startup projects and venture financing ecosystem” has been enacted on October 10, 2024, which introduced more opportunities with funding and introduced a special regulatory regime for digital startups from January 1, 2025, to January 1, 2027, aimed at simplifying operations and encouraging investment [7].

Table 2. Venture Capital in Uzbekistan, 2023

	International venture investors		Local venture investors		Total	
	\$	% of total	\$	% of total	\$	% of total
Local startups	4.3 m	60	2.9 m	40	7.2 m	100
Oversees startups	N/a	N/a	0.8 m.	N/a		
			3.7 m			

The regulations and the impact of the government on the improvement of the startup ecosystem are getting better year on year, however, it is still in its infancy. While the government is fostering the tech startups market, the number of private venture capital organizations is also increasing. By 2023, there were already 10 venture funds in the country: Semurg Ventures, Altergate, Aloqa Ventures, Uzcard Ventures, UzVC, RB ASIA, YELLOWROCKETS.VC, Sturgeon Capital, Fort Ross Ventures, MOST Ventures [8]. Looking at the market overview from January 2022 to June 2023, we can see that it was a moderate \$7.2 million market with 32 investment deals. Sixty percent of the investments

made during the reporting period went to local startups by foreign venture capitalists. Local firms benefited from 78% of the \$3.7 million that domestic venture capitalists gave, while 22% went to overseas startups (see Table 2) [9].

Seventy percent of the \$2.6 million invested came from venture capital supplied by the government. The remaining 30% (\$1.1 million) came from angel and private venture capitalists. When it comes to investing, the private sector is significantly less active than state-owned organizations (Table 3).

Table 3. Uzbekistan’s 2023 Venture Marked by Investor Breakdown

	Government	Local private VCs	Local angel investors	Total
Investors	UzVC, AloqaVentures	Semurg VC, Uzcard Ventures	UzAngels and others	
Investment	\$2.6 m	\$0.8 m	\$0.3 m	\$3.7 m
Share of Total (%)	70	22	8	100

Legislation campaigns and launching private VCs are not enough for the ecosystem. Education programs for both investors and young founders are needed to raise awareness and mentor founders through their journey of building successful startups. On that account, currently, there are several programs like incubators and accelerators, helping startups to improve their ideas, create a business plan, and obtain traction in the market. A startup incubator helps you develop and refine high-potential startup ideas. Incubators often operate locally and provide a host of resources—such as physical space to access as needed—throughout one to five years. Startup accelerators are short, intensive programs that provide education, resources, and mentorship if you're an early or mid-stage founder. Often cohort-based, accelerators are more structured than incubators and outline specific tracks to turn your startup into a scalable business. Some offer multiple programs targeted at different industries or venture stages. Whereas incubators provide the environments and resources to help your ideas succeed, accelerators compress years' worth of learning and growth into the span of a few months [10].

According to [11] and my observations, incubators such as MDIST Business Incubator, Xylem Ignite Innovation Incubator, ITPark, SwiftLaunch, Uzbek-Turkish Incubation Center of the "OLMAZOR STARTUP INKUBATSIYA" and accelerator programs, including Plug and Play Uzbekistan, StartupFactory Uzbekistan, Tumaris Tech, CAT Science Accelerator, Tech4Impact, MGIMO Ventures Tashkent are currently operating in Uzbekistan. Besides there are courses for investors, who want to broaden their portfolio with venture capital, like 'School for Business Angels' by Tumaris Tech[12] and periodic courses by IT Park play a vital role in educating the investors, which in turn fosters the startup ecosystems, leading to the increased number of investors in this area.

CONCLUSION

Based on the aforementioned discussions, the initial phase of introducing venture capital investments and encouraging youth to start their startups has been successful. We can see that in 4-5 years, the number of new startup ideas and minimal viable products in the seed and development stages increased significantly. The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is helping to improve the startup ecosystem by introducing various grants and government VCs. This not only helps existing startups to fund themselves but also encourages others with ideas to start working on building their products. Above mentioned incubators and accelerator programs as well as bootcamps like Startup Weekend Uzbekistan bring a huge value in teaching promising entrepreneurs how to develop a product, how to deal with legal questions, and how to do pitches to attract potential investors quickly. They become a playground of innovative ideas and communities for the youth and investors. However we need to mention that startups and venture capital trends are mostly popular in Tashkent - capital city, which means many young people in regions should come to the capital city to broaden their network and increase their probability of getting funds. This aspect of VC should be reformed and the ecosystem for startups and VC investors should be established and improved in our regions as well.

One of our next goals in the future is definitely to increase successful and profitable businesses in Uzbekistan and help them conquer other countries and launch their products overseas. As technology is being integrated into many aspects of our lives today and Uzbekistan is adopting these innovations quickly in recent years, we can expect that in the future both investors and startups can benefit a lot, building robust products and innovating our daily lives.

REFERENCES

1. S. S. Makhmudov, "Venture Investments: Current Issues and Solutions," *TADQIQOTLAR.UZ*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 16–21, 2024.
2. S. Weik, A. K. Achleitner, and R. Braun, "Venture capital and the international relocation of startups," *Research Policy*, vol. 53, no. 7, p. 105031, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2023.105031
3. G. Qayumova, "The Role of IT and Computer Science Education in Uzbekistan: The Impact of UNESCO Initiatives," *European Journal of Applied Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 16-19, 2024.
4. D. Zufarov, A. Hampel-Milagrosa, V. A. Potluri, and P. Vandenberg, *Uzbekistan's Ecosystem for Technology Startups (No. 9)*, Asian Development Bank, 2023. DOI: 10.22617/WPS230149-3
5. Infogram, "Uzbekistan startup ecosystem overview," <https://infogram.com/uzbekistan-startup-ecosystem-overview-1h7k231dqjxg4xr?live>
6. "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Venture Investments'," available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/-6947651>
7. "Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Measures for the Development of the Startup Ecosystem," available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/7155286>
8. IT-Park Uzbekistan, "Venture capital came to Uzbekistan," доступно: <https://it-park.uz/en/itpark/news/venture-capital-came-to-uzbekistan>
9. Uzbekistan Venture Capital Association, *Uzbekistan Market Research 2023*, доступно: https://uzvca.uz/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Final_ENG-Uzbekistan-Market-Research-2023.pdf
10. Harvard Business School, "Startup incubator vs accelerator," <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/startup-incubator-vs-accelerator>
11. XYZ Lab, "Startup accelerators and incubators in Uzbekistan,"
12. Tumaris.Tech, "Business Angel School," доступно: <https://tumaris.tech/activities/business-angel-school>

